

**PRUJINAGA EGA MATEMATIK MAYATNIKNING DINAMIKASINI
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Annotatsiya: Prujinali matematik mayatnikning kichik tebranishidagi harakat tenglamalarini o'rganish va uning trayektoriyasini tahlil qilish.

Prujinali mayatnik yasash uchun oddiy matematik mayatnikdagi sharchaga bog'langan ipni bikirligi va uzunligi yetarlicha katta bo'lgan prujina bilan almashtiramiz. Keyingi o'rinlarda shunchaki mayatnik so'zini ishlatamiz. Bikirligi katta prujinani tanlashimizga sabab shundaki, biz mayatnikni nafaqat kichik burchaklarga og'dirilgandagi, balki, prujina uzunligining o'zgarishi ham kichik bo'lgan hol uchun tebranishlarini o'rganib chiqmoqchimiz. Bunda biz har xil turdagi ishqalanishlar va qarshilik kuchlarini hisobga olmaymiz. Sistemaning to'la mexanik energiyasi saqlanadi deb qaraymiz.

Sharchaning harakatini o'rganishda qutb koordinatalar sistemasini ishlatish qulaydir. Bunda nuqtaning koordinatasi $A(r, \theta)$ kabi ifodalanadi. Koordinatalar boshini prujinaning osilish nuqtasiga joylashtiramiz. Sharchani moddiy nuqta deb qaraymiz. Bunda sharchaning r koordinatasi prujinaning

o'sha vaqt momentidagi uzunligiga ham teng bo'lib qoladi. $t = 0$ vaqt momentidagi koordinatalar (r_0, θ_0) . Prujinaning deformatsiyasi faqat o'z o'qiga parallel yo'nalishda mavjud bo'ladi va deformatsiya Guk qonuniga bo'ysunadi deb olamiz. Prujinaning bikirligi - k , deformatsiya yo'q bo'lgandagi uzunligi - l_0 . Jismning massasi - m . Yerdagi erkin tushish tezlanishining moduli - g .

Lagranj funksiyasidan foydalanish kuchlarni o'qlarga proyeksiyalagan holda harakat tenglamalarini topishdan qulayroqdir. Aslini olganda, ikkala usuldan yechganimizda ham bir xil natijani olishimiz mumkin. Sistema uchun to'la kinetik energiya T va to'la potensial energiya U ni topamiz. Lagranj funksiyasi $L = T - U$ ga teng.

$$L = \frac{m}{2}(\dot{r}^2 + r^2\dot{\theta}^2) - \left[-mgr \cos \theta + \frac{k(r - l_0)^2}{2} \right]$$

Eng qisqa ta'sir prinsipiga ko'ra esa, quyidagilarni yozishimiz mumkin :

$$\begin{cases} \frac{d}{dt} \frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{\theta}} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial \theta} = 0 \\ \frac{d}{dt} \frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{r}} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial r} = 0 \end{cases} \Rightarrow \begin{cases} m\ddot{r} - mg \cos \theta + k(r - l_0) = 0 \\ mr^2\ddot{\theta} + mgr \sin \theta = 0 \end{cases}$$

Og'ish burchagi va prujina uzunligining o'zgarishi juda kichik ekanligidan quyidagi taqribiy soddalashtirishlarni amalga oshiramiz.

$$\theta \ll 1, \text{ bundan } \sin \theta \approx \theta ; \cos \theta \approx 1 - \frac{\theta^2}{2}$$

$r = z + \frac{mg}{k} + l_0$, $l = \frac{mg}{k} + l_0$, $\frac{z}{l} \ll 1$. Taqribiy hisoblashlar natijasida quyidagi differensial tenglamalar sistemasini olamiz :

$$\begin{cases} \ddot{r} - g \cos \theta + \frac{k}{m}(r - l_0) = 0 \\ \ddot{\theta} + \frac{g}{r} \sin \theta = 0 \end{cases} \quad (I) \Rightarrow \begin{cases} \ddot{z} + \frac{k}{m}z + g \frac{\theta^2}{2} = 0 \quad (1) \\ \ddot{\theta} + \frac{g}{l} \theta - \frac{g}{l^2} z \theta = 0 \quad (2) \end{cases} \quad (II)$$

(I) Tenglamalar sistemasini boshlang'ich shartlar berish orqali komyuterda sonli yechib, kichik bo'lmagan tebranishlar uchun ham grafiklarini olishimiz mumkin. (II) Tenglamalar sistemasini kichik tebranishlar uchun ishlatsakda, koordinatalarning vaqtga bog'lanish tenglamalarini sonli yechmasdan turib keltirib chiqara olamiz. Buning uchun differensial tenglamalarni ishlashda qo'l keluvchi chiziqshtirish metodidan foydalanamiz.

(II) tenglamalar sistemasidagi θ^2 va $z\theta$ hadlar nisbatan juda kichik bo'lib, $z(t)$ va $\theta(t)$ tenglamalarga kichik o'zgartirishlar kiritadi. Buni hisobga olgan holda, quyidagicha usulda taqribiy yechimlarni keltirib chiqaramiz: (1) tenglamada θ^2 hadni kichik deb hisoblab tashlab ketamiz va $z_1(t)$ yechimni olamiz va (2) tenglamaga bu yechimni qo'yish orqali bizga kerak bo'lgan $\theta(t)$

yechimni topamiz. Xuddi shunga o'xshash $\theta_1(t)$ ni topish orqali $z(t)$ ni topamiz. Boshlang'ich shartlarni ham qo'llab o'tamiz. $t = 0$ da $z = z_0$.

$$\ddot{z} + \frac{k}{m}z = 0, \quad \ddot{\theta} + \frac{g}{l}\theta = 0 \Rightarrow z_1(t) = z_0 \cos\left(\sqrt{\frac{k}{m}}t\right), \quad \theta_1(t) = \theta_0 \cos\left(\sqrt{\frac{g}{l}}t\right).$$

$$\ddot{z} + \frac{k}{m}z + g \frac{\theta_1(t)^2}{2} = 0 \quad \ddot{\theta} + \frac{g}{l}\theta - \frac{g}{l^2}z_1(t)\theta = 0$$

Hosil qilgan tenglamalarimizni yechish va boshlang'ich shartlarni qo'yish orqali quyidagi yechimlarni olamiz:

$$z(t) = z_0 \cos\left(\sqrt{\frac{k}{m}}t\right) + \left(\frac{gm\theta_0^2}{4k} + \frac{g\theta_0^2}{4\left(\frac{k}{m} - \frac{4g}{l}\right)}\right) \cos\left(\sqrt{\frac{k}{m}}t\right) - \frac{gm\theta_0^2}{4k} - \frac{g\theta_0^2}{4\left(\frac{k}{m} - \frac{4g}{l}\right)} \cos\left(2\sqrt{\frac{g}{l}}t\right)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \theta(t) = & \theta_0 \cos\left(\sqrt{\frac{g}{l}}t\right) + \\ & + \frac{gz_0}{l^2} \left[\left(\frac{\theta_0}{2\left(\frac{k}{m} + 2\sqrt{\frac{k}{m}}\sqrt{\frac{g}{l}}\right)} + \frac{\theta_0}{2\left(\frac{k}{m} - 2\sqrt{\frac{k}{m}}\sqrt{\frac{g}{l}}\right)} \right) \cos\left(\sqrt{\frac{g}{l}}t\right) - \right. \\ & - \frac{\theta_0}{2\left(\frac{k}{m} + 2\sqrt{\frac{k}{m}}\sqrt{\frac{g}{l}}\right)} \cos\left(\left(\sqrt{\frac{k}{m}} + \sqrt{\frac{g}{l}}\right)t\right) - \\ & \left. - \frac{\theta_0}{2\left(\frac{k}{m} - 2\sqrt{\frac{k}{m}}\sqrt{\frac{g}{l}}\right)} \cos\left(\left(\sqrt{\frac{k}{m}} - \sqrt{\frac{g}{l}}\right)t\right) \right] \end{aligned}$$

Endi esa, avvalo, z dan r ga va undan keyin qutb koordinatalar sistemasidan dekart koordinatalar sistemasiga o'tish orqali $x(t)$ va $y(t)$ larni topamiz.

$$z_0 = r_0 - \frac{mg}{k} - l_0, \quad z(t) = r(t) - \frac{mg}{k} - l_0;$$

$$y(t) = -r(t) \cos \theta(t), \quad x(t) = r(t) \sin \theta(t).$$

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